

Digitized Agritourism as the Hub of Multifaceted Economic Development

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Abstract:- Rural Tourism is considered to be a direction with high potential by the UNWTO(World Tourism Organization),whose stimulation is thought of as a factor of small and medium business sustainability.

The Covid-19 pandemic has been causing unprecedented damage to tourism sector. Authorities of many countries have responded immediately to the crisis.

UN Women Organization in cooperation with the Georgian Farmers' Association has submitted the bill for Agrotourism Development to the parliament Agrarian Committee for Agritourism development (still without response).The article observes the potential results that can be might be achieved with the implementation of the indicated above law, as well as the prospects for the development of agritourism or rural tourism and the potential for digitalization in this sector.

The development of agritourism as an independent tourism direction will be a kind of multiplier for business in local community and also for national economy. The novelty of the proposed study is that digitization can connect traditional agriculture and modern trends of tourism. Agri sector, digitization of Agri-tourism and mutual cooperation will offer international customers a completely exclusive product. Creating a new industry and attracting additional financial resources from outside the country, for the development of the country's economy can be considered as a variety of exports, which is a novelty of the presented research. In this respect, agritourism can be considered as one of the alternative ways of promoting sustainable and multifunctional development of a specific community or region of Georgia as well as whole country.

Keywords:- Tourism, rural Tourism, Agritourism Digitalization, export, bill.

I. INTRODUCTION

World Tourism Organization (WTO) considers high potential of rural tourism, stimulation of which is thought to be a factor of economic stability for small and medium businesses.

Even before the pandemic, Georgia, in particular the Women's organization together with the Georgian Farmers Association has submitted a bill (draft) on Agritourism Development to the Agrarian Committee of Parliament.

Covid- 19 pandemic has caused an unprecedented damage to the whole world, especially to one of the main economic sectors - tourism, in both developed and developing countries. 100-up to 120million direct jobs have been abolished, 54% of the tourism workforce, which include women and young people's livelihood were left without any income due to pandemic crisis.

In response to this critical situation many countries responded instantly in order to maintain the consumer activity as well as the viability of the sector, for which the governments have allocated funds.

Conservation of the third largest export category (tourism industry) in the global economy give the significant and further development, has been made possible by the development and digitization of various mechanisms for the promotion of domestic tourism in a number of countries.

Numerous studies have been carried out to analyze the Georgian agro-tourism market, to develop its potential and to determine its strategic directions on which to base development of agro-tourism in Georgia which consequently will lead to the solution of many accompanying tasks.

Parallel to some benefits for the private sector, agritourism as independent direction of tourism development will be a kind of multiplier for both the region and the country's economy. At the same time, agritourism can be considered as "Export variety" in the sense that Consumer (tourist) having accumulated funds outside the country purchases domestically produced products however, with the difference that he himself resorts to receive the mentioned service directly from suppliers and manufacturers.

Thus, the agro sector and agro-tourism with digitalization and mutual cooperation, will make it possible to offer a completely exclusive product to international consumers in terms of emerging new industries and attracting additional financial resources from outside the country will help the country's economy to recover.

In this respect agritourism can be considered as an alternative way for developing and promoting the multifunctional and sustainable development of the region.

Taking into account the positive experiences of other countries as well as the studies conducted in Georgia the Draft "Law of Georgia on agro-tourism" which Intends to encourage the sector, was submitted to parliament.

II. PROSPECTS OF THE BILL

The idea of developing agritourism originates from Europe, precisely the European tourism market. The study reveals an interest towards agritourism which is growing every year. Georgia, with its cultural-historical or agrarian-recreational conditions, has got favorable environment for agritourism business development.

Agritourism includes rural, non-urban setting tourism activities, of which the main conditions are agricultural activities, the traditional landscape, the rural environment and the host itself while the resource - agro-show, constitutes of the activity and local food product. Agritourism is considered as "as a short way to sell a local product - a short supply chain contributes to local market development.

Having analyzed the Italian Agrotourism Regulation Law, certain legal forms have been adapted to Georgia and the bill has been drafted. As you are aware, the development of agritourism is accompanied by features that are typical for only one country when it comes to in successfully developing the task of agro-tourism. Those factors need to be addressed and analyzed which can have both positive and negative effects on the whole process.

With the implementation of the bill and its objectives it will be possible to develop the agritourism, which in itself refers to farming in the regions of Georgia, promoting agriculture and local production, introduction of liberal tax policy, standardization, employment of rural people and encouragement of small farms, Production of products according to standards, services and directions digitization and more.

The bill is clearly defining one of the actors - to be performed by the state, involved in the governing body activities, which is aimed at agritourism to promote indirect subsidies by way of which the analogue is copied from the agritourism or rural legislative framework of tourism regulation of the European countries.

Unfortunately, the main legislative body of Georgia has postponed the bill indefinitely which represents an impeding factor in itself for the development of the sector while the situation is aggravated by the existing issue of the

pandemic situation. Such a delay shows the current government's irresponsible attitude since not only has it not heard the Bill, but nor was it scheduled for review and neither has it been declined.

Beyond the state Agritourism development is supported by the international donor and local organizations as well as the private sector. However, together, DMOs (Destination Management Organization) which is created by collaboration of the above actors, constitutes an additional mechanism for developing agritourism as a potential sector, albeit an existing one despite the efforts, does not show measurable economic shifts in this regard.

Aims and objectives of the bill without state involvement is difficult to achieve. As you are aware, especially in the highland regions of Georgia. The unresolved infrastructure problems as well as digital inequality in most regions of Georgia have not been overcome so far.

In agritourism-loving consumers Considering world trends Promoting authentic services is an easy tool in digital marketing. Similar types of facilities and services can be offered by Georgia's highlands, though Due to the above-mentioned problems the user admission will not have a long-term effect. Popularization of the country by the state in the technological progress and digital era is an effective way to promote tourism and its independent directions.

From the perspective of Agrotourism management, introducing the joint and effective coordination practices which involves the participatory collaboration of various agency administrations (regional and national level) and community involvement. Integrated management in the regions implies successful service providers collaboration, community-based tourism promotion. Agritourism sector integrated management at the regional level will facilitate both sectoral cooperation enhancement as well as the local population involvement in the effective decision-making process of the tourism management system, which is a prerequisite for the decentralization process.

III. AGRO-TOURISM DIGITALIZATION OPPORTUNITIES

Globalization - mainly for the poor, small and developing countries on the one hand constitutes a challenge, and on the other, it is an opportunity to make an equal start as large and developed countries. Nowadays, accelerated technological progress means we can improve traditional industries, such as agriculture and tourism. Technology and digital technology with the help of digital platforms change the economics of doing business abroad. It reduces the cost and time of international interactions and transactions. It creates effective ways of reaching markets and consumer communities globally, they provide businesses with the huge base of potential customers and effective ways to reaching them.

Based on a complex approach, empirical research methods and secondary information analysis were identified as perspectives of agro-tourism digitalization. Having used

the SWAT analysis of digital platforms in various cities and countries (Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Australia, Thailand, Jirano, Bolzano, etc, <https://localalike.com/> <https://www.spain.info/en/discover-spain/agrotourism-spain/> <https://www.agroturisme.cat/> <https://www.agroturisme.cat/> https://www.orbitz.com/Belgium-Agritourism.d17-aaAgritourism.Travel-Guide-Accommodation <https://www.farmstayplanet.com/farm-stay-rural-travel-guides/britain/>) comparison with Georgia's Agrotourism digital platform potential has demonstrated the digitalization of agro-tourism services and supporting the field with e-commerce would help the agro sector directly as well as its accompanying directions in an indirect way.

www.agrogate.worldis the first agritourism online platform in the South Caucasus which offers a traveler vacationing in a traditional village a farm setting adapted to tourism. Cooperation between these two fields in agrotourism industry in combination with the rest in its best form, contributes to job creation, economy development, protection of ecology and stimulates a competitive environment for business.

IV. CONCLUSION

Study of the above cases has showed that the potential of the field could be further grow if it collaborates with the national economy namely, with the fields, including agriculture. This enhanced connection between Tourism and agriculture reinforces the additional cost of services offered and that is an important potential opportunity for the economy diversification, cultural heritage protection, creation of new jobs and the use of labor where possible, integration of different groups into labor activities (e.g., rural women, older generation, employable citizens.)

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